

Properties of TiO₂ doped SnO₂ thin films deposited using jet nebulizer spray pyrolysis technique for sensor analysis

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Abstract

Oxides, metallic materials and functional layers in commercial electronics applications and sensor devices are deposited using the jet nebulizer technique. The coatings of intrinsic and extrinsic varieties of SnO₂ are employed on a large scale of optoelectronic devices. Extra mural studies were also extended towards the various factors of the thin film, the effect of substrate temperature, electrical conductivity, mobility, carrier concentration as well as feasibility of developing high quality conducting oxide thin films. SnO₂-TiO₂ NPs are nanometer-sized, bright, photo stable, bio-specific, non-toxic that would be used to remove the heavy metal analysis. Since TiO₂ and SnO₂ are insoluble in water, less expensive and higher photocatalytic efficiency semiconductors were selected as the photocatalysts and these find applications in the removal of heavy metals from contaminated water sources in addition to the electronic uses. The development of an aqueous and environmental friendlier synthesis route of jet nebulizer techniques for TiO₂: SnO₂ thin films and the characterization of the deposited films, a study on the impact of substrate temperature on the structural, optical, electrical, and morphological properties of TiO₂: SnO₂ films deposited by the JNS pyrolysis technique, the results for the optimization of the temperature for the formation of crystalline TiO₂: SnO₂ films with a Sn-doping concentration, an application of the developed thin films for the effective removal of toxic heavy metals such as lead and mercury were carried out.

Keywords: JNS pyrolysis technique, TiO₂-SnO₂ thin films, Photocatalysts

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